

'Molluscs as evolving constructions' and phylogenetic deconstructivism

“Los moluscos como construcciones en evolución”¹ y el deconstructivismo filogenético

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ABSTRACT

The Frankfurt Evolution Theory, applied to mollusc evolution, is criticized in terms of testability of scientific hypotheses. This method dismisses all the well-corroborated relationships among mollusc groups without any scientific evidence, and pays no attention to character data analyses.

RESUMEN

Se critica el modelo evolutivo de los moluscos basado en la Teoría Evolutiva de Frankfurt en términos de comprobación de hipótesis científicas. El modelo invalida todas las hipótesis de parentesco entre grupos de moluscos, bien corroboradas por otros datos, sin evidencia científica alguna, y no considera en absoluto métodos de análisis de caracteres.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, phylogeny, evolution, cladistics, parsimony

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, filogenia, evolución, cladismo, parsimonia

INTRODUCTION

In the issue 15 (2) of *Iberus*, EDLINGER AND GUTMANN (1997) presented their model for the evolution of molluscs based on the so-called Frankfurt Evolution Theory (FET). As the authors defined it, the FET conceives organisms as energy transforming units and as autoformative constructions (EDLINGER AND GUTMANN, 1997: 52). After an introduction on how metazoans are explained on the basis of 'hydroskeleton apparatuses and hydraulic units', Edlinger and Gutmann expose their 'theory' of molluscan evolution that can be summarized as follows:

1- an annelid-like metameric ancestor gives rise to a proto-polyplacophoran.

2- a proto-polyplacophoran yields four lineages: Polyplacophora (their Placophora), Caudofoveata, Solenogastres (their Ventroplicata), and a proto-Monoplacophora (although this step is not explicit in the text, it can be extracted from their figure 4).

3- a proto-Monoplacophora evolves into Monoplacophora, Scaphopoda, Gastropoda, Cephalopoda and Bivalvia.

Their 'hypothesis' of relationships is summarized by the branching diagram in Figure 1A. All characters supporting the

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well-established relationships among the molluscan classes (*i. e.* [Polyplacophora + Conchifera]; Conchifera; [Scaphopoda + Bivalvia]) are dismissed by the authors. Furthermore, the authors criticize character-analysis (here they mean morphological characters) and molecular data analysis (as another kind of character-analysis):

Nothing useful can come from such traditional approaches which are blind to causal aspects and insensitive for explanatory principles. (EDLINGER AND GUTMANN, 1997: 64)

Later on they continue:

From the methodology applied and the mode of reconstruction of the evolutionary transformations just advocated follows that traditional phylogenetic concepts, form sequences, and cladograms based on usual procedures are not considered valid. (EDLINGER AND GUTMANN, 1997: 64)

After citing a number of reputed scientific papers on molluscan evolution and phylogenetics, they say:

Most morphoclines presented since the last century are highly contradictory, however, all of them have in common an access that arbitrarily selects some features of skeletal or soft body structures. (EDLINGER AND GUTMANN, 1997: 64)

Checking the literature cited, one realizes that the authors have cited 21 of their own references (of a total of 41). Almost all of their references are published as book chapters (6 citations), meeting volumes, or non-peer-reviewed bulletins such as *Natur und Museum* (4 citations) or *Aufsätze und Reden der Senckenbergischen Naturforschenden Gesellschaft* (3 citations). On the other hand, fifteen other references, most of them extremely important contributions to molluscan evolution and systematics, are cited only to be criticized without real arguments or discussion. This is definitely not a constructive contribution to studies of molluscan evolution.

PHYLOGENETIC SYSTEMATICS

Phylogenetic systematics (of both morphological and molecular data) proceeds by using explicit character data matrices provided by the investigator. These data are used to reconstruct hypotheses of evolution.

Because '*Evolution can never be directly observed*' (as Edlinger and Gutmann stated in the first sentence of their article; probably our only agreement), phylogenetic systematics is forced to use historical information (observed characters) to generate hypotheses of relationships. This can be done by using morphological, behavioral, molecular or any other source of observable (and thus refutable) characters.

Fortunately, during the present decade many students of molluscan evolution have contributed to their field with morphological based parsimony analyses (*i. e.* HASZPRUNAR, SALVINI PLAWEN AND RIEGER, 1995; HASZPRUNAR, 1996; MIKELSEN, 1996; SALVINI PLAWEN AND STEINER, 1996; PONDER AND LINDBERG, 1997; REYNOLDS, 1997; VOIGHT, 1997); non-parsimony cladistic analyses (*i. e.* HASZPRUNAR, 1988; COPE, 1996, 1997; SCHELTENA, 1996); or molecular data analyses (*i. e.* TILLIER, MASSELOT, GUERDOUX AND TILLIER, 1994; WINNEPENNINCKX, BACKELJAU AND DE WACHTER, 1994, 1996; STEINER AND MÜLLER, 1996; ADAMKEWICZ, HARASEWYCH, BLAKE, SAUDEK AND BULT, 1997; BONNAUD, BOUCHER-RODONI AND MONNEROT, 1997; HARASEWYCH, ADAMKEWICZ, BLAKE, SAUDEK, SPRIGGS AND BULT, 1997; ROSENBERG, TILLIER, TILLIER, KUNCIO, HANLON, MASSELOT AND WILLIAMS, 1997; WINNEPENNINCKX, STEINER, BACKELJAU AND DE WACHTER, 1998; GIRIBET AND CARRANZ, in press). Although conflicts depending on the use of different data sets obviously exist, at least all these analyses are explicit; the characters employed are described, can be redefined, recoded, and reanalyzed. And this is what makes scientific progress. None of the arguments given by Edlinger and Gutmann fit the requirements of a scientific hypothesis, because are solely based on speculative thoughts.

Figure 1. Relationships of the molluscan classes as hypothesized by EDLINGER AND GUTMANN (1997) (A), and strict consensus of the current morphological hypotheses by several authors cited in the text (B). Note that in the second hypothesis, non-resolved nodes are obtained after collapsing branches through a consensus procedure.

Figura 1. Relaciones filogenéticas de las diferentes clases de moluscos hipotetizadas por EDLINGER AND GUTMANN (1997) (A), y consenso estricto de las hipótesis morfológicas actuales de los diferentes autores mencionados en el texto (B). Nótese que en la segunda hipótesis, los nodos no resueltos se obtienen colapsando las ramas mediante el proceso de consenso.

Parsimony (the most generalized phylogenetic methodology) can be defended and tested in terms of Popperian definitions of scientific testing; every most-parsimonious cladogram is hypothetical, the best possible conclusion at the time based on the available information (KLUGE, 1997; BENTON, 1998). This excludes all phylogenies based on intuition, that must be considered metaphysical propositions, incapable of falsification (PLATNICK AND GAFFNEY, 1977; BENTON AND HITCHIN, 1996). Cladistics has the strength that it does not claim that most-parsimonious hypotheses of relationships are necessarily true, just that they are the best supported. As KLUGE (1997: 93) stated:

The most parsimonious cladogram, the one least refuted, is only the focus of the next round of testing, and so it goes.

For most authors, cladistic parsimony is based in a single assumption: descent with modification. Cladistics uses synapomorphy as evidence, allows for combination of different sources of characters (total evidence: KLUGE, 1989; EERNISSE AND KLUGE, 1993; JONES, KLUGE AND WOLF, 1993; KLUGE AND WOLF, 1993; KLUGE, 1997), and can be falsified by the addition of more data. Hypotheses generated that way have to be tested in the severest manner possible (FARRIS, 1995; KLUGE, 1997):

Falsification and corroboration comprise alternative results of testing. A theory is falsified if it has been refuted by empirical tests, and it is corroborated if it has so far passed relevant tests. (FARRIS, 1995: 106)

Discussing corroboration of scientific hypotheses (the most parsimonious tree(s)), KLUGE (1997: 84) stated that:

A hypothesis is accepted, but only tentatively, when it has withstood the most severe tests available, and when it has done better than any competing hypothesis (sensu LAKATOS, 1993). The tentativeness of acceptance relates to our inability to know the truth.

Clearly, cladistics, and in particular parsimony cladistics, is the best way to approach phylogenetic relationships from a scientific point of view.

MOLLUSCAN PHYLOGENY

Internal relationships among the eight classes of molluscs is certainly a problematic issue. Such a 'phylogenetic enterprise' has been attempted by several authors (GÖTTING, 1980; LAUTERBACH, 1983; WINGSTRAND, 1985; LINDBERG AND PONDER, 1996; SALVINI PLAWEN AND STEINER, 1996), with a consensus (summarized in Fig1b) in the following points:

1- Caudofoveata and Aplacophora constitute the first branches in the molluscan evolutionary tree, although it is still disputed whether they constitute a clade or a grade.

2- Polyplacophora constitutes the sister-taxa of the remaining shell-bearing molluscs (Conchifera).

3- Scaphopoda and Bivalvia are sister groups.

However, relationships of Cephalopoda, Gastropoda and Monoplacophora among each other and with (Scaphopoda + Bivalvia) are still unclear and highly disputed. The addition of molecular data to this issue (WINNEPENINCKX ET AL., 1996; ROSENBERG ET AL., 1997) has hitherto not provided convincing evidence in favour of a particular hypothesis, due probably to the methodology employed, and certainly to poor taxonomic sampling. For example, Winnepeninckx's analysis used 18S rDNA sequences of 1 Caudofoveata, 2 Polyplacophora, 7 Gastropoda, 1 Scaphopoda and 13 Bivalvia. Taxonomic sampling within each class was poor (*i. e.* only 2 of the 5 extant subclasses of Bivalvia were represented), and three of the eight molluscan classes were omitted from the analyses (Aplacophora, Monoplacophora and Cephalopoda), while two classes were represented by a single sequence (Caudofoveata and Scaphopoda).

Failure of one analysis in reconstructing a global molluscan phylogeny is not fatal, since there is a lot of new data to be added. Sampling the appropriate termi-

nal taxa and the number of characters used seem to be crucial issues in phylogenetic reconstruction (WHEELER, 1992) that have been overlooked by some authors, especially some molecular phylogeneticists. But this does not mean that cladistics is a bad methodology, as Edlinger and Gutmann want us to believe.

In addition, the current ease of collecting molecular data is changing systematics in ways unthinkable only a few years ago. While a wide taxonomic sampling is shown to be crucial in molecular phylogenetic analyses (WHEELER, 1992; GIRIBET AND CARRANZA, 1998), analyses with combination of dozens of sequences from multiple genes plus morphology are already beginning to be published (*i. e.* WHITING, CARPENTER, WHEELER AND WHEELER, 1997; WHEELER, 1998). Together with increased computational power, new algorithms of sequence alignment and tree search, and data exploration through sensitivity analyses are applied to phylogenetic reconstruction procedures (WHEELER, 1995, 1996). This is what palaeontologists, morphologists, anatomists, physiologists, molecular biologists

and systematists can contribute to molluscan evolution. But this is also what Edlinger and Gutmann described as '*... traditional approaches which are blind to causal aspects and insensitive for explanatory principles*'. Certainly cladistics, its reliance in observable characters, and its explanatory power is explicit and leaves out '*sacrificium intellectus*' (in the author's words) to discuss on evolution.

'Molluscs as evolving constructions' contributes nothing to our understanding of molluscan phylogeny. It can be dismissed as an essay lacking any hint of scientific method (any real data and statement of methods employed), and I question where the peer-review process has failed in this case.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ADAMKEWICZ, S. L., HARASEWYCH, M. G., BLAKE, J., SAUDEK, D. AND BULT, C. J., 1997. A molecular phylogeny of the bivalve mollusks. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 14: 619-629.
- BENTON, M. J., 1998. Reconstructing the tree of life (book review). *Journal of Evolutionary Biology*, 11: 922-924.
- BENTON, M. J. AND HITCHIN, R., 1996. Testing the quality of the fossil record by groups and by major habitats. *Historical Biology*, 13: 111-157.
- BONNAUD, L., BOUCHER-RODONI, R. AND MONNEROT, M., 1997. Phylogeny of cephalopods inferred from mitochondrial DNA sequences. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 7: 44-54.
- COPE, J. C. W., 1996. The early evolution of the Bivalvia. In Taylor, J. (Ed): *Origin and evolutionary radiation of the Mollusca*. Oxford University Press, London, pp 361-370.
- COPE, J. C. W., 1997. The early phylogeny of the class Bivalvia. *Palaeontology*, 40: 713-746.
- EDLINGER, K. AND GUTMANN, W. F., 1997. Molluscs as evolving constructions: necessary aspects for a discussion of their phylogeny. *Iberus*, 15 (2): 51-66.
- EERNISSE, D. J. AND KLUGE, A. G., 1993. Taxonomic congruence versus total evidence, and amniote phylogeny inferred from fossils, molecules, and morphology. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 10: 1170-1195.
- FARRIS, J. S., 1995. Conjectures and refutations. *Cladistics*, 11: 105-118.
- GIRIBET, G. AND CARRANZA, S., (in press). What can 18S rDNA do for bivalve phylogeny? A response to Steiner and Müller. *Journal of Molecular Evolution*.
- GÖTTING, K. -J., 1980. Origins and relationships of the Mollusca. *Zeitschrift für zoologische Systematik und Evolutionsforschung*, 18: 24-27.
- HARASEWYCH, M. G., ADAMKEWICZ, S. L., BLAKE, J. A., SAUDEK, D., SPRIGGS, T. AND BULT, C. J., 1997. Neogastropod phylogeny: a molecular perspective. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 63: 327-351.
- HASZPRUNAR, G., 1988. On the origin and evolution of major gastropod groups, with special reference to the Streptoneura (Mollusca). *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 54: 367-441.

- HASZPRUNAR, G., 1996. The Mollusca: coelomate turbellarians or mesenchymate annelids? In Taylor, J. (Ed): *Origin and evolutionary radiation of the Mollusca*. Oxford University Press, pp 1-28.
- HASZPRUNAR, G., SALVINI PLAWEN, L. V. AND RIEGER, R. M., 1995. Larval planktotrophy: A primitive trait in the bilateria? *Acta Zoologica*, 76: 141-154.
- JONES, T. R., KLUGE, A. G. AND WOLF, A. J., 1993. When theories and methodologies clash: a phylogenetic reanalysis of the North American Ambystomatid Salamanders (Caudata: Ambystomatidae). *Systematic Biology*, 42: 92-102.
- KLUGE, A. G., 1989. A concern for evidence and a phylogenetic hypothesis of relationships among *Epicrates* (Boidae, Serpentes). *Systematic Zoology*, 38: 7-25.
- KLUGE, A. G., 1997. Testability and the refutation and corroboration of cladistic hypotheses. *Cladistics*, 13: 81-96.
- KLUGE, A. G. AND WOLF, A. J., 1993. Cladistics: What's in a word? *Cladistics*, 9: 183-199.
- LAKATOS, I., 1993. Falsification and the methodology of scientific research programmes. In Lakatos, I., Musgrave, A. (Eds): *Criticism and the Growth of Knowledge*. Cambridge University Press, London, pp 91-196.
- LAUTERBACH, K. -E., 1983. Erörterungen zur Stammesgeschichte der Mollusca, insbesondere der Conchifera. *Zeitschrift für zoologische Systematik und Evolutionsforschung*, 21: 201-216.
- LINDBERG, D. R. AND PONDER, W. F., 1996. An evolutionary tree for the Mollusca: branches or roots? In Taylor, J. (Ed): *Origin and evolutionary radiation of the Mollusca*. Oxford University Press, London: 67-75.
- MIKKELSEN, P. M., 1996. The evolutionary relationships of Cephalaspidia s. l. (Gastropoda: Opisthobranchia): a phylogenetic analysis. *Malacologia*, 37: 375-442.
- PLATNICK, N. I. AND GAFFNEY, E. S., 1977. Systematics: a Popperian perspective. *Systematic Zoology*, 26: 360-365.
- PONDER, W. F. AND LINDBERG, D. R., 1997. Towards a phylogeny of gastropod molluscs: an analysis using morphological characters. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 119: 83-265.
- REYNOLDS, P. D., 1997. The phylogeny and classification of Scaphopoda (Mollusca): an assessment of current resolution and cladistic reanalysis. *Zoologica Scripta*, 26: 13-21.
- ROSENBERG, G., TILLIER, S., TILLIER, A., KUNCIO, G. S., HANLON, R. T., MASSELOT, M. AND WILLIAMS, C. J., 1997. Ribosomal RNA phylogeny of selected major clades in the Mollusca. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 63: 301-309.
- SALVINI PLAWEN, L. V. AND STEINER, G., 1996. Synapomorphies and plesiomorphies in higher classification of Mollusca. In Taylor, J. (Ed): *Origin and evolutionary radiation of the Mollusca*. Oxford University Press, pp 29-51.
- SHELTEMA, A. H., 1996. Phylogenetic position of Sipuncula, Mollusca and the progenetic Aplacophora. In Taylor, J. (Ed): *Origin and evolutionary radiation of the Mollusca*. Oxford University Press, pp 53-58.
- STEINER, G. AND MÜLLER, M., 1996. What can 18S rDNA do for bivalve phylogeny? *Journal of Molecular Evolution*, 43: 58-70.
- TILLIER, S., MASSELOT, M., GUERDOUX, J. AND TILLIER, A., 1994. Monophyly of major gastropod taxa tested from partial 28S rRNA sequences, with emphasis on Euthyneura and hot-vent limpets Peltospiroidea. *The Nautilus*, suppl. 2: 122-140.
- VOIGHT, J. R., 1997. Cladistic analysis of the octopods based on anatomical characters. *Journal of Molluscan Studies*, 63: 311-325.
- WHEELER, W. C., 1992. Extinction, sampling, and molecular phylogenetics. In Novacek, M. J., Wheeler, Q. D. (Eds): *Extinction and phylogeny*. Columbia University Press, New York, pp 205-215.
- WHEELER, W. C., 1995. Sequence alignment, parameter sensitivity, and the phylogenetic analysis of molecular data. *Systematic Biology*, 44: 321-331.
- WHEELER, W. C., 1996. Optimization alignment: the end of multiple sequence alignment in phylogenetics? *Cladistics*, 12: 1-9.
- WHEELER, W. C., 1998. Sampling, groundplans, total evidence and the systematics of arthropods. In Fortey, R. A., Thomas, R. H. (Eds): *Arthropod Relationships*. Chapman and Hall, London, pp 87-96.
- WHITING, M. F., CARPENTER, J. M., WHEELER, Q. D. AND WHEELER, W. C., 1997. The Strepsiptera problem: phylogeny of the holometabolous insect orders inferred from 18S and 28S ribosomal DNA sequences and morphology. *Systematic Biology*, 46: 1-68.
- WINGSTRAND, K. G., 1985. On the anatomy and relationships of recent Monoplacophora. *Galathea Report*, 16: 1-94.
- WINNEPENNINGCKX, B., BACKELJAU, T. AND DE WACHTER, R., 1994. Small ribosomal subunit RNA and the phylogeny of Mollusca. *The Nautilus*, suppl. 2: 98-110.
- WINNEPENNINGCKX, B., BACKELJAU, T. AND DE WACHTER, R., 1996. Investigation of molluscan phylogeny on the basis of 18S rRNA sequences. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, 13: 1306-1317.
- WINNEPENNINGCKX, B., STEINER, G., BACKELJAU, T. AND DE WACHTER, R., 1998. Details of gastropod phylogeny inferred from 18S rRNA sequences. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 9: 55-63.